

MULTI-SCALE, MULTI-PHYSICAL PROCESS SIMULATION OF THE PRODUCTION OF MULTICURVED CFRP REINFORCEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

In this work the authors present the latest simulation and experimental results for the production of multi-curved composite frames manufactured by resin transfer moulding. For the simulation of the infusion process and subsequent structural spring-in behaviour of the cured structure was divided in unit cells that have been used for both simulations. In a first step the draping behaviour of the dry preform was simulated using ANSYS ACP to derive the reinforcement directions and shear angles. In a second step the infusion process of different sheared unit cells and the final part under the relevant boundary conditions were simulated by the conventional finite element software PAMRTM. Out of the simulation the amount and position of the resulting pores and dry spots were assessed. The unit cells were further used to calculate the stiffness tensor and thermal expansion as function of the temperature including the expected resin properties during cure. The temperature dependent stiffness tensor and relative thermal expansion between the mould and the infiltrated preform served as input for the determination of the geometrical changes after the demoulding step – spring-in effect. Non-destructive ultrasonic testing and shape measurement were performed to validate the predicted dry spots and the global deformation behaviour after demoulding.

1 INTRODUCTION

In order to bring the advantages of fibre reinforced polymers – high specific strength and stiffness – into markets where mass production is essential e.g. car industry or specific aircraft parts such as

stringers or frames, automated manufacturing techniques have to replace the common manual production. Depending on the part to be manufactured, liquid composite moulding techniques like Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) or Vacuum Infusion (VI) or Automated Fibre Placements (AFP) are such automated production techniques [1, 2]. The most important steps in the production of complex composite parts by RTM are the proper placement of the preforms to adjust the required orientation of reinforcement, to reach a full impregnation of the preform and to compensate distortions after demoulding step. Depending on the complexity of the parts geometry and the type of the dry preform distortion in combination with inhomogeneous flow conditions within the mould, the infiltration can arise fibre misalignment and the inclusion of pores and dry spots that influence the structural behaviour of the composite part. The finite element simulation of the production process followed by structural analyses of the components with production induced imperfections – like fibre misorientations, pores and geometrical changes – could strongly help the manufacturers in understanding the behaviour of real – imperfect – composite parts. Within this paper the authors concentrate on the aspects of process simulations such as draping, spring-in effect and dry spot detection on multi-curved frames manufactured by resin transfer moulding.

2 MODELING AND SIMULATION CONCEPT

The structure to be analysed was a multi-curved composite frame made of carbon fibre 5H satin weave fabric infiltrated with RTM 6 resin. For process simulation the component was subdivided into unit cells. In a first step, the same unit cell was used to determine the permeation coefficients for the RTM simulation and the temperature dependent stiffness and thermal expansion tensor for the simulation of the spring-in behaviour. In a second step, draping of the woven fibre reinforcement was simulated to determine the resulting fibre orientations and shear angles. Both parameters were projected onto the part to obtain the local fibre directions for the spring-in simulation. In parallel, the unit cell for the determination of the permeation coefficients was sheared to a number of shear angles to evaluate the influence of the shear angle on the relative permeation coefficients. Once the permeation coefficients and local fibre orientations were determined both parameters were projected on the part for the final infiltration simulation. Figure 1 shows an overview of the chosen simulation procedure.

Figure 1: Overview of the chosen simulation procedure.

3 UNIT CELL

3.1 Model

The used unit cell model shown in Figure 2 was a 5H satin weave, composed of yarns in 0° and 90° direction interrupted by pure resin pockets. The model was built in TexGen and imported in ANSYS.

Figure 2: The unit cell model of the 5H satin weave.

For both simulation environments the fibre volume fraction of the yarns was set to 83 vol%, in this way a nominal fibre volume content of 58 vol% for the whole unit cell was targeted.

3.2 Determination of elastic and thermal properties for spring-in simulation

For the determination of the stiffness and thermal expansion tensor of the unit cell, the different material properties of the resin pockets (green colour in Figure 2) and the yarns (violet colour in Figure 2) were assigned to the dissimilar parts of the unit cell. The resin part was modelled as a temperature dependent isotropic elastic material whereas the yarns were modelled as a transverse-isotropic material with the parallel direction parallel to the yarn orientation. The transverse-isotropic material behaviour was derived from classical micro-structural formulas shown below, where the index “f” was used for the fibre properties and the index “m” was used for the resin properties. The material properties of the fibres were assumed to be temperature independent whereas the resin was assumed to depend on the temperature during curing. “E” was used for the Young’s modulus, “G” for the shear modulus and “v” for the Poisson’s ratio. The subscripts “par” and “nor” mean parallel and normal to the fibre direction.

$$E_{par} = E_{f,par} \cdot \varphi + E_m \cdot (1 - \varphi) \quad [3] \quad (1)$$

$$E_{nor} = \frac{E_m}{1 - \nu_m^2} \cdot \frac{1 + 0.85 \cdot \varphi^2}{(1 - \varphi)^{1.25} + \frac{E_m}{(1 - \nu_m^2) \cdot E_{f,nor}} \cdot \varphi} \quad [4] \quad (2)$$

$$G_{nor,par} = G_m \cdot \frac{1 + 0.4 \cdot \varphi^{0.5}}{(1 - \varphi)^{1.45} + \frac{G_m}{G_{f,nor,par}} \cdot \varphi} \quad [5] \quad (3)$$

$$G_{nor,nor} = \frac{E_{nor}}{2 \cdot (1 + \nu_{nor,nor})} \quad [3] \quad (4)$$

$$\nu_{nor,par} = \varphi \cdot \nu_f + (1 - \varphi) \cdot \nu_m \left[\frac{\left(1 + \nu_m - \nu_{nor,par} \cdot \frac{E_m}{E_{par}} \right)}{\left(1 - \nu_m^2 + \nu_m \cdot \nu_{nor,par} \cdot \frac{E_m}{E_{par}} \right)} \right] \quad [6] \quad (5)$$

$$\alpha_{par} = \frac{\alpha_m \cdot E_m \cdot (1 - \varphi) + \alpha_{f,par} \cdot E_{f,par} \cdot \varphi}{E_m \cdot (1 - \varphi) + E_{f,par} \cdot \varphi} \quad [3] \quad (6)$$

$$\alpha_{nor} = \alpha_m - (\alpha_m - \alpha_{f,nor}) \cdot \left[\frac{2 \cdot (\nu_m^3 - \nu_m^2 - \nu_m - 1) \cdot 1.1 \cdot \varphi}{1.1 \cdot \varphi \cdot (2 \cdot \nu_m^2 + \nu_m - 1) - (1 + \nu_m)} - \frac{\frac{\nu_m \cdot E_{f,nor}}{E_m}}{\frac{E_{f,nor}}{E_m} + \frac{(1 - 1.1 \cdot \varphi)}{(1.1 \cdot \varphi)}} \right] \quad [7,8] \quad (7)$$

The following tables show the material properties of the RTM6 resin from curing temperature down to room temperature and the temperature independent properties of the carbon fibre (AS4). The used coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) value between 180°C and 179°C was based on a linear shrinkage due to cure of 1.9% [9].

Temperature [°C]	E_m [MPa]	ν_m	α_m [m/mK]
180	32	0.49	0.018
179	290	0.45	6.9×10^{-5}
160	2000	0.35	6.9×10^{-5}
22	2900	0.35	6.9×10^{-5}

Table 1: Material properties of RTM6 resin [9].

$E_{par,f}$ [GPa]	$E_{nor,f}$ [GPa]	$G_{nor,par}$ [GPa]	$\nu_{nor,par}$	$\alpha_{par,f}$ [m/mK]	$\alpha_{nor,f}$ [m/mK]
231	13	50	0.23	-0.6×10^{-6}	1.2×10^{-5}

Table 2: Material properties of AS4 fibre [3].

Out of the material properties shown in Table 1 and 2 and the formulas (1) to (7) the temperature dependent stiffness and thermal expansion tensors of the used unit cell were calculated by applying unit deformations. The results are shown in Table 3.

Temperature [°C]	E_x, E_y [GPa]	E_z [GPa]	$G_{x,y}$ [GPa]	$G_{x,z}, G_{y,z}$ [GPa]	$\nu_{x,y}$	$\nu_{x,z},$ $\nu_{y,z}$	α_x, α_y [m/mK]	α_z [m/mK]
180	45.0	0.36	0.17	0.04	0.001	0.54	2.26×10^{-5}	0.013
179	59.5	2.97	1.44	0.41	0.004	0.55	3.16×10^{-7}	6.3×10^{-5}
160	70.3	10.1	8.74	2.26	0.012	0.48	2.10×10^{-6}	5.5×10^{-5}
22	71.8	10.9	12.1	3.04	0.013	0.42	2.48×10^{-6}	5.0×10^{-5}

Table 3: Calculated properties of the 5H satin weave unit cell.

In order to use the features of ANSYS ACP – to project fibre directions and shear angles onto the finite element mesh of the component – both tensors were used to calculate the equivalent unidirectional (UD) properties of one layer of a [0/90] cross-ply laminate.

Temperature [°C]	E _x [GPa]	E _y , E _z [GPa]	G _{x,y} , G _{y,z} [GPa]	G _{x,z} [GPa]	ν _{x,y}	ν _{x,z} , ν _{y,z}	α _x , [m/mK]	α _y , α _z [m/mK]
180	90.0	0.36	0.17	0.04	0.28	0.57	1.28x10 ⁻⁶	0.013
179	115	2.97	1.44	0.41	0.28	0.55	-5.3x10 ⁻⁷	6.3x10 ⁻⁵
160	129	10.1	8.74	2.26	0.28	0.48	-1.5x10 ⁻⁷	5.5x10 ⁻⁵
22	133	10.9	12.1	3.04	0.28	0.42	4x10 ⁻⁸	5.0x10 ⁻⁵

Table 4: Calculated properties of the equivalent UD material.

3.3 Determination of permeability for infusion simulation

Similar to the determination of the material properties for the calculation of the spring-in effect, the permeability coefficients of the different parts of the unit cell were calculated based on micro-mechanical formulas summarized in Table 5 for the yarn region.

Model type	In fibre direction	Perpendicular to fibre direction	Parameter
Lubrication approximation	$\frac{8}{53} \frac{(1-V_f)^3}{V_f^2} r_f^2$	$\frac{16}{9\pi\sqrt{6}} \left(\sqrt{\frac{V_{f\max}}{V_f}} - 1 \right)^2 r_f^2$	$V_{f\max hex} = \frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{3}}$
Self-consistent method	$\frac{r_f^2}{8V_f} \left(\ln \frac{1}{V_f} - \frac{(1-V_f)^2}{(1+V_f)^2} \right)$	$\frac{r_f^2}{8V_f} \left(\ln \frac{1}{V_f} - (3-V_f)(1-V_f) \right)$	-

r_f – fibre radius, V_f – fibre volume fraction

Table 5: Formulas for the determination of the permeability coefficients parallel and normal to the fibre direction in the yarn region. [10, 11]

At higher volume fractions the resulting permeability values of the two models are almost equal. For the infiltration simulation permeability values of 5.96E10⁻¹³ m² in fibre direction, and 1.61E10⁻¹⁵ m² parallel to fibre direction were calculated using the lubrication approximation model. The permeability of the matrix region was set to 1.5E10⁻¹¹ m², with this value the filling time of the original (un-sheared) unit cell equals the filling time of a homogeneous unit cell (no division of yarn and matrix regions), thus the global permeability of the unit cell is resulting the measured permeability value (Chapter 4.1.1).

The following figure show three examples of unit cells during infiltration – one un-sheared and two sheared by 12° shear angle used for the determination of the average permeability coefficients in x and y-direction.

Figure 3: Flow front propagation in unit cells (un-sheared and sheared configurations).

The results of the two sheared configurations led to an anisotropy factor (ratio of filling times) of 1.03, whereas no un-isotropic behavior was seen on the original (un-sheared) unit cell. Due to this very small un-isotropy of the sheared unit cells, the first infiltration simulations (shown in the next chapter) were performed assuming isotropic permeability coefficients.

4 INFILTRATION SIMULATION ON MACROSCOPIC SCALE

4.1 Results of infiltration simulation (macroscopic scale)

Based on the determined isotropic permeability coefficient of the un-sheared unit cell, parameter studies of different infiltration strategies were investigated. Primary goal of these simulations were the estimation of the infiltration time and the appearance of macroscopic dry spots. Due to the fact, that the preforms cannot be perfectly trimmed to the edges to perfectly fit the mould, gaps at the edges of the part have to be taken into account. The following figures show 3 different investigated injection strategies.

Figure 4: Investigated injection strategies – red dot: injection point, blue dots: outlet points, blue area: gap at the edges of the part.

All three injection strategies have been analyzed using the commercial finite element software PAM-RTM assuming a constant isotropic permeability. The frame was divided in two regions – the central region containing the dry woven preform and the edge region with different gap sizes. The used permeation coefficients for the central region were 10^{-11} m^2 out of the analyses of the un-sheared unit cell and 10^{-8} m^2 for the gap region. The used viscosity of the resin for these simulations was 0.1 Pas. The following figures show the filling times using an infiltration pressure of 1 bar and potential regions of dry spots for all three injection strategies.

Figure 5: Filling times for injection strategy V1 using a 1 mm gap (left side) and a 5 mm gap (right side).

Figure 6: Filling time (left side) and dry spots (blue regions on the rights side) for injection strategy V2 for a 1 mm gap.

Figure 7: Filling time (left side) and dry spots (blue regions on the rights side) for injection strategy V3 for a 1 mm gap.

Out of these simplified first simulation results the following conclusions can be drawn. In general, the width of the gap has a significant influence on the filling times for all injection strategies. When using injection strategies V2 and V3 with the outlet vents at the corners, the quick flow front propagation along the gaps (race-tracking effect) leads to dry spots during the infiltration (blue regions in the right side of Figure 6 and 7). Therefore, such injection strategies should be avoided. For injection strategy V1 in the beginning the resin flows primarily along the gaps filling the whole gap region followed by a slow propagation from the gap region towards the vent positioned in the middle of the frame. It has to be noted that the position of the vent has to be carefully adjusted. Based on the results injection strategy V1 was selected for further detailed analysis and investigations described in the next chapter.

4.1.1 Measurement of permeability

For more detailed analysis the flow front propagation in the dry preform lay-up was measured under constant pressure condition to determine the potential anisotropic permeation coefficients caused by the imperfect flow front propagation due to stacking effects of the laminate. Figure 8 shows the propagating flow front and the evaluated permeation coefficients in the main direction of the ellipse.

	FWD1	FWD2	Average
K1 [m ²]	4.60E-12	4.71E-12	4.65E-12
K2 [m ²]	2.65E-12	4.01E-12	3.33E-12
K1/K2	1.75	1.17	1.45
α rot to 0°	35	28	31.5

Figure 8: Flow front propagation (left side) and calculated permeability coefficients of two measurements (rights side).

It can be seen that the flow front propagates in the shape of an ellipse with an aspect ratio of around 1:1.45 indicating a slight anisotropic behaviour.

4.1.2 Infiltration results based on measured permeability

The measured permeability coefficients were used to analyse injection strategy V1 by mapping the anisotropic permeability coefficients onto the part. For the simulation a pressure difference of 2 bar and a constant viscosity of 0.1 Pas was assumed. Figure 9 shows the propagation of the flow front during the infiltration.

Figure 9: Flow front propagation in the part after 180 s (top left), 362 s (top right), 478 s (bottom left) and 657 s (bottom right) taking the anisotropic permeability into account.

It can be seen that due to the anisotropic flow front propagation dry spots at one location of the part appear as indicated by the green to blue area in the bottom, right position of Figure 9. In order to avoid these dry spots an additional vent at that position is required.

5 SPRING-IN SIMULATION

For the spring-in simulation a 3D finite element model of the part to be manufactured was built in ANSYS ACP. In a first step a shell model was built and extruded to create the 3D model. The elastic tensor shown in Table 4 was used for the definition of the material properties. In order to avoid an explicit modelling of the mould it was simulated by fixed boundary conditions at the part – mould interface. For the shrinkage of the mould material only the relative thermal expansion tensor between the mould and the part was taken in account. The calculated properties for the case of an Aluminium mould are shown in Table 5, in comparison Table 6 shows the case of an Invar mould.

Al mould	20	160	179	180
$\alpha_{xx,rel}$	-2.50E-05	-2.52E-05	-2.55E-05	-2.37E-05
$\alpha_{yy,rel}$	2.52E-05	3.03E-05	3.77E-05	1.33E-02
$\alpha_{zz,rel}$	2.52E-05	3.03E-05	3.77E-05	1.33E-02

Table 5: Calculated temperature dependent properties of the equivalent UD material.

Invar mould	20	160	179	180
$\alpha_{xx,rel}$	-1.96E-06	-2.15E-06	-2.53E-06	-7.20E-07
$\alpha_{yy,rel}$	4.82E-05	5.33E-05	6.07E-05	1.33E-02
$\alpha_{zz,rel}$	4.82E-05	5.33E-05	6.07E-05	1.33E-02

Table 6: Calculated temperature dependent properties of the equivalent UD material.

The displacement of the part relative to the mould was simulated using a 0.005 mm thick interlayer made of a soft, nearly incompressible material between the part and the mould surface. Stress free conditions were used as starting conditions at the curing temperature of 180°C. Then the part was cooled in several steps from 180°C to 20°C: shrinkage due to cure from 180°C to 179°C; stress built up in the mould from 179°C to 160°C and 160°C to 22°C; demoulding step with removed boundary conditions from the part surface cooling from 22°C to 20°C.

As already mentioned, the first step in the simulation of the spring-in effect was the draping of the dry preform on the mould to derive local fibre orientation and shear angles. Figure 10 shows the result of the geometrical draping simulation.

Figure 10: Results of the draping simulation – distribution of the shear angle over the part.

The derived fibre orientation and shear angle results were used to define the local direction of reinforcements as basis for the spring-in simulation. The following figures show the shrinkage of the part relative to the stress free conditions after demoulding for the Al and the Invar mould.

Figure 11: Shrinkage of the part relative to the stress free condition after demoulding for the Al (top) and the Invar mould (bottom).

Using different mould materials, the difference in the global deformation after demoulding can be clearly seen (Figure 11). Out of the simulation results the changes in the shape of different cross sections along the major axis of the mould were evaluated and compared to the measurements on manufactured real parts. The most important type of deformations can be summarized as following:

- change of length of frame – depends strongly on mould material,
- change of cross section profile – reduction of angle,
- reduction of curvature in the x-z plane,
- reduction of curvature in the y-z plane.

Finally the Al mould was selected for the production of the first parts as described in the next chapter. For the Al mould the major geometrical changes due to the spring-in effect are:

- total length change: 6 mm,
- total change of angle in the cross section: 1.77° (details are shown in Figure 12),
- maximum deformation in the x-z plane: 1.6 mm,
- maximum deformation in the y-z plane: 1.5 mm.

Figure 12: Change of profile due to spring-in effect (blue – un-deformed profile, orange deformed profile), the angles show the change of the individual parts of the profile.

6 VERIFICATION

Based on the simulation results an aluminium mould was manufactured by Alpex and infiltration experiments were performed by Airbus Helicopters. The shape of the mould cavity was corrected based on the results of the spring-in-simulation to achieve a part with the proper geometry. Figure 13 shows the parts of the mould, the mounted mould in the press during the manufacturing of the part and the final part after demoulding.

Figure 13: Parts of the mould (top left), mounted mould inside the press during the manufacturing of the part (top right) and the final produced part after demoulding (bottom).

After demoulding the quality of the part was investigated by ultrasonic inspection and the regions with dry spots were marked with white paint as shown in the bottom part of Figure 13. It can be seen that the dry spots appear at the simulation predicted locations on the part. The shape of the part was measured by a 3D optical system and compared to the target geometry. In total 7 cross section have been selected and analysed in detail showing deviations from the target geometry smaller than 0.4 mm which was within the pre-defined tolerances of the part.

9 CONCLUSIONS

Within this paper the authors presented the results of the multi-step process simulation and experimental verification of manufacturing high quality multi-curved frames for aircraft applications. The results can be summarized as following:

- The used unit cell approach for the determination of the stiffness, thermal expansion and permeability tensor was very effective for the prediction of the required material input data for the different simulation steps.
- The location of the predicted dry spots by the infiltration simulation based on the permeability measurements coincide with the position of resin arm regions found on the manufactured parts.
- The definition of the geometry of the mould's cavity based on the results from the spring-in simulation lead to production of parts with the required geometric tolerances.

In the continuation of the project improvement in the models will be done to further improve the final geometry of the parts by tailoring the predicted material properties of the used unit cells.

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